

Notas Nomenclaturales / Nomenclatural Notes

A replacement name for *Pelophila* Dörjes, 1968 (Xenacoelomorpha: Acoela, Convolutidae)

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ABSTRACT

The following replacement name in Acoela (Xenacoelomorpha, Acoelomorpha) is proposed: *Acoelopelophila* Ceccolini & Cianferoni **nom. nov.** pro *Pelophila* Dörjes, 1968 nec Dejean, 1821. Further, the following new combination is also established: *Acoelopelophila lutheri* (Westblad, 1946) **comb. nov.**

Key words: Acoelomorpha; homonym; new combination; nomenclature change.

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RESUMEN

Se ha detectado un homónimo más moderno entre los Acoela (Xenacoelomorpha, Acoelomorpha) y se propone el siguiente nombre sustitutivo: *Acoelopelophila* Ceccolini & Cianferoni **nom. nov.** pro *Pelophila* Dörjes, 1968 nec Dejean, 1821. Se da también la siguiente nueva combinación: *Acoelopelophila lutheri* (Westblad, 1946) **comb. nov.**

Palabras clave: Acoelomorpha; cambio de nomenclatura; homónimo; nueva combinación.

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Xenacoelomorpha Philippe *et al.* 2011 is a small phylum of bilateral invertebrates recently established, removing them from Platyhelminthes (Philippe *et al.*, 2011). They seem to be the sister group of the other bilateral animals (Rouse *et al.*, 2016; Cannon *et al.*, 2016) and are divided in the subphyla Xenoturbellida Bourlat *et al.*, 2006, with 6 species known (WoRMS, 2021), and Acoelomorpha Ehlers, 1985, including about 435 species, most of them accommodated in the order Acoela Uljanin, 1870 (Zhang, 2013).

We detected a homonym genus name in Acoelomorpha Acoela and herein we propose the new substitute name for it.

REPLACEMENT NAMES

Dörjes (1968: 114) established the new genus name *Pelophila* to accommodate two new species: *P. cavernosa* and *P. pachymorpha*. Currently the name is still in use, even if both the original combinations are not still accepted. Indeed *Pelophila pachymorpha* is now

classified in the genus *Pelochildia* Faubel & Warwick, 2005, whilst *Pelophila cavernosa* (the type species of the genus) is considered a subjective junior synonym of *Pelophila lutheri* (Westblad, 1946) (Tyler *et al.*, 2021).

However, the name *Pelophila* had already been used in Zoological Nomenclature. Dejean (1821: 7) introduced this name to accommodate the species *Carabus borealis* Paykull, 1790 (Coleoptera, Carabidae) in his catalogue. Dejean's name is still in use (Huber & Marggi, 2017; Rees, 2021).

Therefore, *Pelophila* Dörjes is a junior homonym of *Pelophila* Dejean and, since no synonym is available, it must be replaced according to ICZN (1999, Arts. 60.1, 60.2). Herein we propose *Acoelopelophila* Ceccolini & Cianferoni **nom. nov.**

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ETYMOLOGY

The new name remarks the classification of the genus in the order Acoela, adding the prefix *Acoel-* and the linking vowel *-o-* to the original name. Feminine gender.

SYSTEMATICS

Family CONVOLUTIDAE Graff, 1905

Genus *Acoelopelophila* Ceccolini & Cianferoni **nom. nov.** = *Pelophila* Dörjes, 1968 nec Dejean, 1826

Species *Acoelopelophila lutheri* (Westblad, 1946) **comb. nov.** = *Pelophila lutheri* (Westblad, 1946) = *Aphanostoma lutheri* (Westblad, 1946) = *Mecynostomum lutheri* (Westblad, 1946) = *Praeaphanostoma lutheri* Westblad, 1946 = *Pelophila cavernosa* Dörjes, 1968 (type species)

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References

Cannon, J.T., Vellutini, B.C., Smith III, J., Ronquist, F., Jondelius, U. & Hejnol, A., 2016. Xenacoelomorpha is

the sister group to Nephrozoa. *Nature*, 530 (7588): 89-93. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature16520>

Dejean, P.F.M.A., 1821. *Catalogue de la collection de Coléoptères de M. le Baron Dejean*. Libraire de Crevot, Paris. VIII + 136 pp. <https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.11259>

Dörjes, J., 1968. Die Acoela (Turbellaria) der deutschen Nordseeküste und ein neues System der Ordnung. *Journal of Zoological Systematics and Evolutionary Research*, 6 (1): 56-452. <https://doi.org/10.1111/j.1439-0469.1968.tb00431.x>

Huber, C. & Marggi, W., 2017. Tribe Pelophilini Kavanaugh, 1996. In: Löbl, I. & Löbl, D. (eds.). *Catalogue of Palaearctic Coleoptera. Archostemata – Myxophaga – Adephaga. Revised and Updated Edition. Volume I*. Brill, Leiden: 63.

ICZN—International Commission on Zoological Nomenclature, 1999. *International Code of Zoological Nomenclature. 4th Edition*. The International Trust for Zoological Nomenclature, London. XXIX + 306 pp. Available from <https://www.iczn.org/the-code/the-code-online/> [accessed 21 Oct. 2021].

Philippe, H., Brinkmann, H., Copley, R.R., Moroz, L.L., Nakano, H., Poustka, A.J., Wallberg, A., Peterson, K.J. & Telford, M.J., 2011. Acoelomorph flatworms are deuterostomes related to *Xenoturbella*. *Nature*, 470 (7333): 255-260. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature09676>

Rees, T., 2021. *The Interim Register of Marine and Nonmarine Genera*. Available from <https://www.irmng.org> [accessed 21 Oct. 2021].

Rouse, G.W., Wilson, N.G., Carvajal, J.I. & Vrijenhoek, R.C., 2016. New deep-sea species of *Xenoturbella* and the position of Xenacoelomorpha. *Nature*, 530 (7588): 94-97. <https://doi.org/10.1038/nature16545>

Tyler, S., Artois, T., Schilling, S., Hooge, M. & Bush, L.F., 2021. *World List of Turbellarian Worms: Acoelomorpha, Catenulida, Rhabditophora*. Available from <http://www.marinespecies.org/turbellarians> [accessed 21 Oct. 2021].

WoRMS, 2021. *World Register of Marine Species*. Available from www.marinespecies.org [accessed 22 Oct. 2021].

Zhang, Z.-Q., 2013. Animal biodiversity: an update of classification and diversity in 2013. In: Zhang, Z.-Q. (ed.). *Animal Biodiversity: an outline of higher-level classification and survey of taxonomic richness* (Addenda 2013). *Zootaxa*, 3703: 1-82. <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.3703.1.3>